

The Impact of Internet Gaming among the Young Learners

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Abstract: The main aim of this research article is to study the positive and negative impact of internet gaming and mobile phone usage among the young graduates belongs to Tamil Nadu during this lockdown period. In addition, the purpose of this article is to explore the relations between internet gaming and its impact on learning. During this period of coronavirus, the young learners faces social exclusion and is at home. It leads to stress problems and depression problems. Social media and internet gaming sites are a new means of drainage and entertainment for the young learners. Students' feedbacks and social networking time were considered in this research. Their feedback was tested by means of an opinion survey. The internet play time and status update times were taken as a measuring tool. Furthermore, online chats, online education and online play times were taken into consideration. This research shows that the use of internet gaming and mobile devices is twice as long. In addition, this research clearly demonstrates the increase in online learning time, online search time and online chat time during this lockdown period. This article illustrates the increase in knowledge about social media among young aged learners. Moreover, mobile media have created a group attitude among young people. Through this research, it is observed that there is a vast change in Smartphone usage found among rural youngsters. In addition, this research demonstrates that the addition of internet games and changes in behaviour and impact may increase as this social dissociation continues. Artificial intelligence based on the behaviour of user groups can be an area of thrust to study behaviour patterns among young learners.

Keywords: Internet gaming, learning, stress, depression, digital tools, opinion survey, COVID-Lockdown

1. INTRODUCTION

Research related to internet gaming and learning has been developing since 2005. Research on Internet gaming disorder-IGD is current research area which has a potential outputs. During the peak of COVID-19 period the internet play time among the learners' was increased. Also, the usage of various social media tools like WhatsApp, YouTube, Facebook, Twitter and TikTok were developed among the learners. There

was no psychometric tools available to study the internet gaming disorder among the different aged people. Digital addiction developed due to social exclusion and idealness during this COVID period. According to American Psychological Association DSM-5 was used as a mental health tool to study the mental disorders. But there was no fruitful evidence for its uniqueness due to internet game playing mental disorders. DSM-5 was also used to study the disorders due to alcohol, marijuana, and tobacco. The world health organisation announced the internet gaming addiction as a new disorder among the patients. According to the American Journal of Psychiatry, internet gaming was new area to study. Some evidences showed that there was a connection between internet gaming and depression. National academy of sciences listed the internet gaming disorder as a behavioural disorder. Also, it showed the need of research into the area of internet gaming.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to RUISHE (2021), COVID-19 pandemic created a big impacts on physical and mental problems among the children and young aged learners. RUISHE research showed the relationships between the stress factors, internet game disorders, and learning. RUISHE studied the gender differences in the pandemic period. Duan et al. (2020), research showed that the huge impact on socialisation due to the COVID-19 isolation. In addition, children and adolescence aged people separated from their peers, teachers, and groups. The pandemic and school closure affected their routine life activities. Moawad (2020), conducted research on pandemic situation and conflicts among the family members and stress. According to Moawad, academic stress developed due to the limitation of resources such as library, materials, online system, exam plans and poor teaching methods. According to Chen et al, there was a relationship exist between the variables such as internet gaming disorder and psychological distress. Furthermore, Chen's

research showed the difference before and after the pandemic period. Their research showed the vulnerability among the adolescence due to the development of internet gaming disorder, prolonged stress, mental and behavioural health. Dong's research showed the links between Internet gaming addiction and psychological factors among young aged people and adolescents. A longitudinal study was conducted by Jeong, E. J., Ferguson, et al. (2020), to study the academic stress and self-control among the Korean students. Their research found out the development of academic stress during the pandemic period.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This opinion survey research paper tries to study the relationship between internet game play hours and learners' performance among the young graduates of computer science. A well-planned questionnaire was distributed through Google form to understand the experience of B.Sc computer science graduates. Total 50 computer science graduates were selected from the sample. The simple random selection method was applied to select the sample. The questionnaire contained total thirty numbers of questions related to internet play and exam performance. Convenient sampling method was used to study the relevant sample. The questionnaire contained three parts related to internet game play hours, learners' exam performance, and health related questions.

The questionnaire includes

- Opinion of computer science graduates
- Previous exam performance
- Health related questions

4. FINDINGS SUGGESTIONS

Graduates' opinion on internet game play

- ❖ 75 percent of young graduates opined that internet game play helped them to get relaxation.
- ❖ 90 percent of young graduates opined that internet game play had an impact on their study hours.
- ❖ 94 percent of young graduates felt that the internet game play time should be reduced.
- ❖ 65 percent of young graduates accepted the addictive behaviour due to the internet games
- ❖ 52 percent of young graduates felt that internet game play motivated them to study the digital subjects

Previous exam performance

- ❖ 65 percent of internet game players had good exam performance. (60 and above marks)
- ❖ 20 percent of internet game players had low exam performance. (50 to 60 marks)
- ❖ 10 percent of internet game players had very low exam performance. (40 to 50 marks)

- ❖ 62 percent of young graduates accepted the addictive behaviour and their exam performance
- ❖ 80 percent of young graduates felt that internet game play helped them to relax from education

Health related questions

- ❖ 60 percent of internet game players had stress related problems
- ❖ 15 percent of internet game players had depression related psycho somatic disorders
- ❖ 70 percent of internet game players had finger and hand joint pains (short period of time)
- ❖ 68 percent of internet game players accepted the eye problems due to their game playing nature

5. LIMITATIONS

This research considers the opinion of young graduates between the age groups of 21 to 25. To study the opinion of B.Sc computer graduates, this research considered the top three private universities belongs to Tamil Nadu. This research considers the internet game play hours among the graduates. Only high internet play hours i.e., more than four hours, were considered to study its impacts. Two popular internet games such as PUBG and Free Fire were considered for this research.

6. CONCLUSION

There are so many psychological tests are available to study the psychosomatic problems and addictive behaviour among the young aged people. Even though test like personality test, emotional intelligent test, intelligent test, stress test, motivational test, and therapies are available, still there is a lack of study found in the area of internet gaming and addictive behaviours. The research result clearly shows that there are positive and negative impact among the computer science graduates. The findings of this survey paper clearly shows the links between health problems and internet game play among the computer science graduates. Furthermore this research shows the negative links between the internet game playing addiction and exam performance. There is a negative relationships found between the two variables such as stress and internet game play among the graduates.

References

1. RUI SHE et al. (2021). How COVID-19 stress related to schooling and online learning affects adolescent depression and Internet gaming disorder: Testing Conservation of Resources theory with sex difference, Centre for Health Behaviours Research, JC School of Public Health and Primary Care, Faculty of Medicine, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, China.
2. Duan, L., Shao, X., Wang, Y., Huang, Y., Miao, J., Yang, X., & Zhu, G. (2020). An investigation of mental health status of children and adolescents in China during the outbreak of COVID-19. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 275, 112–118.

3. Moawad, R. A. (2020). Online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic and academic stress in university students. Volume. 12(1 Sup2), 100–107
4. Dong, H., Yang, F., Lu, X., & Hao, W. (2020). Internet addiction and related psychological factors among children and adolescents in China during the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID19) epidemic. *Frontiers in Psychiatry*.
5. Jeong, E. J., Ferguson, C. J., & Lee, S. J. (2019). Pathological gaming in young adolescents: A longitudinal study focused on academic stress and self-control in South Korea. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 48(12), 2333–2342.
6. <https://www.psychiatry.org/patients-families/internet-gaming>